

Modular programme for Education and Training
EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR

M#1 Daily Physical Activity and Play

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For further information on the EduPASS Project please follow the link:

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS for Early Childhood Educators

The following are the proposed six core modules for Early Childhood Educators education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Early Childhood Educators should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for ECE education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(ECEC\)](#). The ECEC describes the most important the proposal for key principles of a [Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(2014\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing an Early Childhood Educator education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS ECE education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Play	<p>The module teaches the theoretical basis of the concept of holistic development of children, focusing on changes experienced by children aged 3 to 6 years.</p> <p>It emphasizes the importance of physical activity and play in children's overall development and well-being and highlights the benefits of physical activity during childhood, as well as the potential risks of inactivity on overall health. Additionally, recommendations for children's physical activity levels, strategies for implementation, and the development of skills for assessing the recommended daily physical activity level for children are provided.</p> <p>Finally, a theoretical background for developing intervention programs aimed at improving children's daily physical activity levels is presented. It includes practical workshops and the development of skills for designing and implementing programs to enhance children's daily physical activity levels.</p>

2	Principles of Educating Children	<p>This module aims to guarantee the comprehensive development of children through physical education. For this, different learning units, based mainly on the game, will be carried out such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motor stories • music, dance and movement • energetic games • games with balls • activities that involve balance, development of laterality, coordination and body awareness • manipulative and construction games
3	Inclusive Teaching	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical foundations of the concept of inclusion. This includes the legal background (e.g., UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and national legislation), the requirements and goals of inclusion, and didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies for inclusive teaching. • provide opportunities to practically apply and reflect about the principles, methods, and resources of inclusive teaching using specific teaching/case scenarios.
4	Fundamental Movement Skills, Play and Motor Skill Assessment	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical basics of the concept of fundamental movement skills and play and their importance for children. This includes the structure of fundamental movement skills, their role in children’s development, and didactic principles and methods to promote fundamental movement skills and play. • provide guidance on the practical use of the principles, methods, and resources of teaching/promoting fundamental movement skills and play. • introduce both the theoretical knowledge and the practical skills to objectively measure fundamental movement skills of children using motor tests
5	Hands-on Teaching	<p>This module is designed to enhance the practical skills of Early Childhood Educators through direct participation in learning activities. Through a hands-on approach, participants will develop key skills to foster high-quality interactions with children and create an inclusive learning environment.</p> <p>During the module, Early Childhood Educators will engage in interactive exercises and receive immediate feedback, allowing them to directly apply the pedagogical techniques learned to their educational settings. Strategies for observation and documentation, group dynamics management, and conflict resolution will be addressed, all focused on adapting pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children.</p>

6	Plan, Reflect and Learn	<p>The application of teaching skills, observation and effective decision making is essential to fulfil teaching PAMPS for early childhood and is a cross-cutting capability that should be developed in all ECEs at each stage of their development. The ECE plans, evaluates and reflects each practice and event seeking improvements. In addition, this personal evaluation and reflection underpin a process of ongoing learning and professional development. An important element of this process is the ECE's efforts to with other ECEs in the process.</p> <p>Reflection plays a vital role in early childhood settings. It provides continuous professional development, support, and feedback for all members involved and gives ECEs a safe space to discuss challenging experiences and related feelings. It lays the groundwork for ongoing professional development through consistent self-reflection, community support, and emotional awareness. It's critical that educators can manage the feelings that come with stress to support children's development, communicate effectively with co-workers and families, and find job satisfaction.</p> <p>Questioning what learning and development is taking place to make meaning of what has been observed is crucial for ECE. ECE students should be able to describe why the events are significant to the child and to describe why this experience was important for the child involved.</p>
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Module Structure

Core Module	Daily Physical Activity and Play
Module Number	1
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To clarify the concept of holistic development of children. • To emphasize the importance of regular physical activity (PA) and play for children's fitness, physical and mental health, as well as for their cognitive, social, and emotional development. • To provide recommendations for daily physical activity in children. • To provide knowledge for monitoring and assessing physical activity levels in children. • To provide knowledge and skills for designing and delivering different activities and programs supporting daily physical activity in children in various non-formal settings.
Module Description	<p>The module consists of four courses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 1.1: This course teaches the theoretical basis of the concept of holistic development of children, focusing on changes experienced by children aged 3 to 6 years. • Course 1.2: This course emphasizes the importance of physical activity and play in children's overall development and well-being. It highlights the benefits of physical activity during childhood, as well as the potential risks of inactivity on overall health. • Course 1.3: This course focuses on recommendations for children's physical activity levels, strategies for implementation, and the development of skills for assessing the recommended daily physical activity level for children. • Course 1.4: This course provides a theoretical background for developing intervention programs aimed at improving children's daily physical activity levels. It includes practical workshops and the development of skills for designing and implementing programs to enhance children's daily physical activity levels.
Module Duration	30 hours
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym
Methodology	<p>Course 1.1: Class-based lectures and presentations, independent fieldwork (observation of children), work in small groups.</p> <p>Course 1.2: Class-based lectures and presentations, independent fieldwork, work in small groups, focus group discussions.</p> <p>Course 1.3: Class-based lectures and presentations, independent fieldwork, work in small groups, focus group discussions, specific task scenarios, and practical workshops.</p>

	Course 1.4: Class-based lectures, work in small groups, field-based sessions, peer teaching, focus group discussions, and practical workshops.
Coaching Materials	Logbook/reflection book, toolkit
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gallahue, D., & Ozmun, J. (2006). <i>Understanding Motor Development: Infants, Children, Adolescents, Adults</i> (6th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill. • Haywood, K.M.; Getchell, N. (2020). <i>Life Span Motor Development</i>, 7th ed.; Human Kinetics: Champaign, IL, USA, 2020 • Malina, R., Bouchard, C. & Bar – Or, O. (2004). <i>Growth, Maturation and Physical Activity</i> (Second Edition). Champaign: Human Kinetic, Illinois • Santrock, J. (2008). <i>Life–Span Development</i> (Eleventh edition) New York: McGraw – Hill Book Company • Steene-Johanessen, Hansen, Dalene, et al. (2020). Variations in accelerometry measured physical activity and sedentary time across Europe - harmonized analyses of 47,497 children and adolescents. <i>Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act</i>, 17(1):38. doi: 10.1186/s12966-020-00930-x. • World Health Organization. (2019). <i>Guidelines on Physical activity, sedentary behavior, and sleep for children under the age of 5</i> https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/325147/WHO-NMH-PND-2019.4-eng.pdf • World Health Organization (2018). Physical Activity: http://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/physical-activity; 2018
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Early Childhood Educator Programmes
Module structure (each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 1.1: Child holistic development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture/Seminar ○ 4 h Self-directed work ○ 2 h Workshop/ work in small groups • Course 1.2: Importance of Physical Activity and Play for Children's Holistic Development and Overall Well-being <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture/Seminar ○ 4 h Self-directed work ○ 2 h Workshop/ work in small groups/focus groups discussion • Course 1.3: Recommendations for Daily Physical Activity for Children <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture/Seminar ○ 2 h Self-directed work ○ 2 h Practical workshop/ work in small groups/specific tasks scenarios/focus group discussion • Course 1.4: Design of Interventional Programs for Increasing Daily Physical Activity of Children in Different Settings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture/Seminar ○ 4 h Workshop/practical experience/ work in small groups ○ 2 h Seminar/ Workshop/focus groups discussion
Learning outcomes	The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they teach:

<p><i>for Early Childhood Educators</i></p>	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of how to motivate and engage children. • Knowledge of the child's interests and preferences • Pedagogical knowledge • Knowledge of the basis of a child's motor development 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication skills • Promoting fun and enjoyment • Skills and abilities for how to motivate children and engage them in different forms of physical activity
	<p>Attitudes: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive attitude toward physical activity and children engagement in PA regularly • Enthusiasm to work with children at a younger age • Motivation to work with children and motivation to work for children well - well-being. 	<p>Values: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Inclusion • Responsibility • Promoting positive changes
<p>Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i></p>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to support the children they teach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):</p>	
	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of their interests and preferences • Understanding of what motivates them to be engaged in different forms of daily physical activities • Knowledge of different activities in PAMPS 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Cooperation skills • Motivation skills
	<p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Empathy • Respect • Enthusiasm 	<p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation • Empathy

<p>Module Outcomes <i>action oriented outcomes and results for educators</i></p> <p><i>(based on Quality Statements from EU Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care, 2014)</i></p>	<p>The educator will have taken the first step towards being able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide educational experiences that encourage participation based on children's individual interest and abilities; strengthen social inclusion and embrace diversity • Implement a curriculum based on pedagogic goals, values and approaches which enable children to reach their full potential holistically, respecting individual differences between children • Collaborate with children, colleagues and parents in providing different possibilities for engagement in different forms of daily physical; reflect on his/her own practice • Embrace opportunities for observation, reflection, planning and teamwork related to educational experiences • Engage in monitoring and evaluation, focused on what is in the best interest of the child
<p>Connection to other Core Module</p>	<p>Module 4: Fundamental Movement Skills, Play and Motor Skill Assessment</p>

Course Structure

Course Title	Child Holistic Development		
Course Number	1.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>This course provides the theoretical basis of holistic child development, focusing on changes experienced by children aged 3 to 6 years. It provides an overview of holistic development and explains in depth the aspects of physical growth, motor development, cognitive development, and socio-emotional development. The course emphasizes the interrelation between all developmental domains, particularly in relation to movement, physical activity, and play, and their impact on the overall development, health, and well-being of children.</p> <p>The main objective of the course is to highlight the importance of a holistic approach to child development, specifically in relation to movement, and to understand the significance of understanding developmental specifics at a particular age, especially during early childhood.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / S	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: The Concept of Holistic Development and Domains of Development
	SDL	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Knowing the Individual as a Key Approach in Learning about Child Holistic Development
	W	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Principles, methods and resources in promoting holistic development
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept of holistic development • Specifics of motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional development at 3 – 6 years old children • The importance of holistic approach from the aspect of physical activity 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observing a particular child or several children independently at the age of 3 – 6 years • Focus observation of changes that occur in every developmental domain, identifying similarities and differences between different children 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work in small groups for preparing teaching activities based on theoretical lectures and independent observations and work 	

Course Title	Importance of Physical Activity and Play for Children's Holistic Development and overall Well-being		
Course Number	1.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The course teaches about the significance of physical activity and play in children's overall development and well-being. It highlights the benefits of physical activity during childhood, emphasizing its impact on physical, motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional aspects of development and focusing on the importance of physical activity for maintaining health, proper growth, and overall well-being. The course also identifies the potential risks of inactivity on children's overall health and provides evidence-based experiences from the COVID-19 period.</p> <p>The main objective of the course is to stress the importance of regular physical activity for a child's holistic development, health, and overall well-being.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / S	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Importance of Daily Physical Activity and Children's Play
	SDL	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Physical Activity vs Physical Inactivity in Children: Benefits and Potential Risks
	W	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: From Studies to Actions
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focusing on the importance of daily physical activity in children for holistic development and overall health and well-being. 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Readings of evidence-based studies for the impact of physical activity or inactivity on children's health, well-being and overall development of children Emphasis on study results and experiences and evidence during COVID-19 pandemics 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work in small groups/focus groups discussion for preparing a toolkit with infographic slides for benefits of regular physical activity of children and potential risk from inactivity 	

Course Title	Recommendations for Daily Physical Activity for Children		
Course Number	1.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>This course focuses on recommending physical activity levels for children, strategies for implementation, and developing skills for assessing the recommended daily physical activity level for children. It addresses country-specific benchmarks for daily physical activity in children. It also identifies the responsibilities and defined actions of parents, teachers, coaches, and stakeholders in achieving it.</p> <p>The main objective of the course is to emphasize the recommended daily physical activity levels for children of different ages, equip teachers with skills for assessment, and underline the responsibilities of all involved parties in achieving the recommendations.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / S	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: WHO Recommendation for Daily Physical Activity Quality of Life of Children
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Policies vs Reality
	W	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Call for Actions
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focusing on the WHO recommendations for daily physical activity and quality of life in children; pyramid of physical activity and nutrition. 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Readings of evidence-based studies for benchmarks, country-specific recommendations, and country-specific reports for the achieved level of PA and quality of life in children Approaches in evaluating daily PA level Identification of existing policies and actions and identification of responsibilities among different stakeholders 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work in small groups/focus groups discussion for preparing teaching activities that will support identified recommendations and preparing an action plan suggested to different stakeholders 	

Course Title	Design of Intervention Programmes for Increasing Daily Physical Activity of Children in Different Settings		
Course Number	1.4		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>This course provides a theoretical background for developing intervention programs aimed at supporting children's daily physical activity levels. It provides insights for teachers on how to create an environment that supports and stimulates physical activity daily, how to integrate movement with other learning activities, incorporate movement and play during nonstructured time, involve parents etc.</p> <p>The main objective of this course is to teach teacher educators how to incorporate movement and physical activity in different parts of the day and within the educational process, apart from time dedicated to physical education.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / S	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Key Aspects of Designing Interventional Programs for Promoting Physical Activity Daily
	W / PE	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Design of Programs that Support Children`s Daily Physical Activity
	S / W	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Guidance and Support for Implementation
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focusing on identifying possibilities for implementing physical activity for children in different settings Learning the key aspects that help design successful programs and implement them in practice 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work in small groups for designing programs in different settings that will support children`s daily PA, and their holistic development and provide a possibility to meet WHO recommendations 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus group discussion that will help teacher educators identify best practice examples, possible obstacles How to overcome them as well as to identify ways to implement designed programs in their everyday setting 	